

1 **06.06.2025, Sorbonne**

2 **Interviewee: Angelo Monoriti**

3 **Interviewers: Filippo Martini & Francesco Torres Cruz**

4 S00: Go ahead, let's start.

5 S01: So, then—first of all, beyond the presentation for purely legal
6 purposes—I'd ask you to tell us a bit about who you are. Who better than
7 you to introduce... yourself? You're certainly the most suitable person to do
8 that.

9 S00: This is the most difficult part; I'm usually very brief on this. So,
10 my name is Angelo Monoriti, I'm a lawyer, and—let's say—passion led me to
11 study the themes of negotiation; so today I'm an adjunct professor, at
12 LUISS and at Unitelma Sapienza, and I try to pass this on to students...
13 nothing more.

14 S01: And so, in terms of negotiation, you deal with it both on the
15 educational/training side, in the academic sphere, and then on the
16 practical side as well—is that right?

17 S00: Yes. Let's say the path—which may be the interesting part—began in
18 practice. I felt a need, because traditional legal training, classical
19 legal education, was insufficient for the work I was doing. As a lawyer
20 assisting companies at negotiation tables, it didn't really help me. So I
21 started to study negotiation on my own, in a traditional way, building up
22 the theoretical side. Then I realized it was something worth passing on to
23 younger generations. That's where the idea came from—for example, to
24 write
25 my book, *NegotiAction* in English (*NegoziAzione* in Italian). The idea was
26 simply to make that path shorter for those who might want to start earlier.
That's all.

27 S01: So it began as your own need, first as a person, and then you
28 said—well—you thought it might be worth transmitting.

29 S00: Exactly. I felt this because there were no real studies available—I
30 hadn't had the chance to study negotiation, and even today many still
don't.

31 So my technical legal training felt insufficient for the work I was doing.
32 I was spending less time in court and more time consulting inside
33 companies,
34 and I sensed that something was missing. I found that missing piece in the
study of negotiation. That's how it started.

35 S01: Eh, this step is very interesting; it's also very genuine, in the
36 sense that we start as learners...

37 S00: ...we always remain learners.

38 S01: ...and then we move into a role where, in any case, there's also the
39 desire to transmit. (.) It's nice to start from the roots from this point
40 of view, because sometimes we focus on the second part and forget a lot of
41 the rest.

42 S00: Yes, as I said, it came from a need. At the beginning it wasn't easy

43 to find a path, because—as you know—there was no institutional
44 framework,
45 no real courses. Now—I’m not that old—but today there are many more.
46 Back
47 then it was difficult. To give you an idea, the only option was to search
48 for books, starting from *Getting to Yes* and then moving on to others,
49 trying to reconstruct the field. That, let’s say, was the path (..)

48 S01: First of all, thank you for this—this insight, in a certain way also
49 personal. Thanks.

50 S00: I avoid anecdotes, because you told me that everything is going to be
51 transcribed—and many of those I could tell are covered by confidentiality.

52 S01: You’ll tell us with the mic off. Instead, now I’d get into the core
53 questions, which you surely had a chance to read—because, as a good
54 negotiator, you even anticipated the request. So I ask you: we’re facing a
55 lot of changes in the European context, and some of these concern political
56 transformations, climate, economic, social pressures—which obviously also
57 change the way we approach negotiation. And so I ask: which of these
58 changes has had the greatest impact on your professional day-to-day?

..3.1.1. Challenges

59 S00: Well, that’s an extremely difficult question, because if we’re talking
60 about external changes—shifts in the outside world that affect how we
61 negotiate—it’s hard to single out just one. But the overall perception is
62 that everything has become more complex. If I had to choose, I’d say the
63 impact of technology. Not for any mystical reason, but because, in my view,
64 negotiation presupposes human interaction. And now we’re facing a whole
new

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65 front: negotiations with artificial intelligence, or even against
66 intelligence—but still based on that premise of human interaction. What I
67 notice is that people—all of us—are much more accustomed to technology,
68 whose function is essentially to replace direct communication. It started
69 with simple tools like SMS and WhatsApp, and now we have artificial
70 intelligence. This has influenced negotiation because people seem more
71 distracted, less attentive, less able to really focus when you speak with
72 them. Perhaps for me it was easier, since I went through a different path,
73 but I’ve especially noticed this among younger people: because they rely

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74 so
75 much on these tools, sometimes they struggle to stay engaged in real
76 interaction. That’s the change I’ve felt most strongly. Of course, I don’t
77 want to downplay other important changes you mentioned— like wars, and
78 so
79 on—which also create fear and stress. But if we focus strictly on
80 negotiation, I’d say the biggest change is this: it’s harder to get people
to truly listen for any length of time. We send more emails and WhatsApps
instead of actually talking to each other.

81 S01: So the ability to build the relationship—that’s what I understand.

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82 S00: Yes, that’s definitely what I’ve noticed most in recent times. It has
83 required putting much more focus on the relational aspects of
84 negotiation—making sure the other person is really listening, has the

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concentration, and even pausing if you realize they're not. And this is harder today, because the tendency is to be faster, more "quick," to get straight to the point.

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S01: So technology impacts the mindset within the relationship more than it does as a tool; that's interesting, because perhaps here too we're very projected toward the future—toward what it can give us. (.)

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S00: Right, right. I don't want to misinterpret the question—the point is which change has had the biggest impact on how we negotiate. I'd put it this way: the main change I've noticed in others is the effect of technology. On the other hand, I haven't yet seen the opposite—that technology has already gone so far as to fully replace human interaction. That hasn't reached me yet; maybe it will in time. So yes, what I've really observed is technology as a factor that has influenced the relational side.

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S01: Very interesting—very, very interesting. It seems that, from this point of view, you bring it back to a relational dimension. The subtitle of your book is "the manual of human interaction," so it recalls this aspect. It seems to be something you care about. It should be for all negotiators, right?

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S00: Yes, yes. And let me add—if we want to open another front, without taking too much time—the other issue is artificial intelligence: technology that replaces the human, even in a negotiating context. This opens enormous

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scenarios, even raising the question of whether we can still call it negotiation. I actually have an article on this coming out soon on Federalismi.it. I'm not saying there's a clear yes-or-no answer, but one could argue that the very concept of negotiation is inextricably linked to humans. The word itself was created to describe a human activity. So between two machines, for example—is that really negotiation, or is it just calculation?

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S01: From this standpoint, the legal aspect returns: when there's automation, there must always be the possibility of a second-level interaction with a human.

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S00: Exactly. Otherwise—if that interaction disappears, who are we then? Even what we're doing here might no longer make sense. The point is—going back to your observation—without human interaction, does it even make sense to speak of negotiation? We can try to describe it, but between two machines, is it really negotiation or just calculation? I'm convinced about this. And then, where does the evolution of our species go? I believe we evolve through negotiation—through conflicts that we then resolve by negotiating. They're two sides of the same coin that allows us to grow. But if we stop doing it, that's the real problem: artificial intelligence tends to replace negotiation for economic reasons—because humans are too slow. That's the point. AI's business is precisely to replace the slowness of human negotiation. I'll stop here, otherwise...

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S01: Maybe we'll come back to this, if you like. There's another question that's connected, in a way. We've talked about the systemic difficulties

130 brought by these changes. So I ask you: what's the most demanding
131 negotiation you've taken part in—or had the chance to observe?

..3.1. Case Description

132 S00: Keeping confidentiality in mind, I can share one case: a negotiation
133 facilitated by a mediator—technically a mediation—with three parties
134 involved. The situation was very difficult because it concerned a claim for
135 damages by a mother who alleged—let me use their words—defamation or
136 improper use of her son's image. He had died, and that image had
137 mistakenly
138 been used in an audiovisual product. It was an extremely delicate case,
139 with many parties involved—these productions have multiple players,
140 lawyers
141 in the middle—but above all there was a mother who had lost her child and
142 suddenly saw his image appear again after some time. I can't go into the
143 details, but I don't want to avoid your question. Why do I say it was the
144 most difficult? Because reaching agreement wasn't only about
145 numbers—already a major challenge, with positions very far apart, ranging
146 from astronomical damages on one side to outright rejection on the other.
147 The real issue was managing the emotional impact of that fact on a grieving
148 mother. The solution, I have to say, was creative—in the way we mean it:
149 there was no monetary compensation; we reached another kind of solution.
150 And here's the point I care about: we got there simply by following the
151 path we study and teach in negotiation. It was extremely complex, and I
152 remember telling myself, "let's see if what we study and practice really
153 works." So we followed the steps: managing the relationship first, then
154 moving from positions to interests. So I think this gives hope to everyone.
155 And to be precise: it wasn't about personal brilliance or skill. If I had
156 any merit, it was simply sticking to the principles we follow—even here at
157 this conference—so we can tell ourselves, and others, that the process
158 makes sense. Nothing "personal," just following a method. And it worked.

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157 S01: I'd say you've already covered the implicit questions here—namely,
158 what made it difficult. It seems it was the human dimension, to come back
159 to what we're saying.

160 S00: Yes. And the same applies to other cases that come to mind. As for
161 the
162 substantive dimension—well, I admit I'm not exceptional there. With a legal
163 background (my fellow lawyers will kill me for this), our "legal training"
164 doesn't involve much work with numbers or math. But when there are
165 complex
166 substantive issues, the sciences—math, economics, and so on—can help.
167 What
168 I find hardest, though, are the relational aspects. The emotional impact
169 can even cause a complete breakdown—which is often the starting point:
170 communication is interrupted, the parties aren't talking to each other.
171 Getting past that initial shock, that blockage, and then overcoming the
172 emotional barrier—that, in my view, is the most difficult part.

170 S01: So you start by reconstructing communication even before the
171 relationship.

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172 S00: Exactly. And I think that when there are filters in the middle—like
173 companies or organizations—it can sometimes (not always) be easier,
because

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the person representing the group can also act as a filter...

S01: ...also in a healthy sense.

S00: Exactly. But when it's personal matters, like the one I described, that's where the real difficulty lies—because we've all experienced something like that.

S01: The other question you've already touched on: which central variables allowed you to reach—or not reach—agreement?

S00: Look, I'll go straight to a concept that, in my view, is absolutely central: interests. What was decisive here was staying focused on identifying and satisfying the mother's interests. And there's an added difficulty: you can't just look at material or physical interests, but also psychological ones. In this case, the primary interest of a mother is, of course, her children. Everything was built around that. And in this situation, it wasn't just about one child; she had others as well.

S01: So you managed to create added value by reconstructing the interests.

S00: Yes, but let me be clear: this wasn't easy. It may sound simple now, but at the time we were dealing with a very polarized situation—a claim for monetary damages. Making that shift, from the position—"you owe €100,000"—to the question "what is the real interest of a mother?" sounds easy, but that's what actually allows new ideas to emerge. And let me add: it isn't easy because along the way you encounter a lot of skepticism. When you try to do this, people will tell you, "it won't work," "it won't work," "it makes no sense," "what could a mother want other than money?" You hear

everything. This isn't a criticism—it's normal. It's probably a matter of negotiation culture, which we are still building—and that takes time.

S01: It's certainly a very delicate topic, and in part it ties into the next question, with a circular path that carries forward what we've said so far. The conference theme: what are we doing? We're trying to build a bridge between the academic world and the world of practitioners. Where do you see the widest gap between academic knowledge and practice?

S00: Good question. I do see a gap. Speaking about Italy, if I may, on the academic side I don't see many well-structured courses in negotiation. We do have mediation—which you know very well—and that's fine, but in my view

it's too focused on the legal framework, on the architecture, while the real heart of it is negotiation itself. To simplify, I'd put it like this: academia still hasn't focused on or invested in negotiation courses. And without that, you don't create practitioners; you don't create professionals with that background. Those who do get it, get it on their own—so I'm talking mainly about young people. But that means we're not really building for the future. And for those who are already working, where can they learn it? Only on their own, through the kind of path I described earlier—reading books. It's possible, but it's not easy, and it takes much longer. So I'd sum up the gap like this: leaving aside past and present, the question is whether we are truly investing in the future. And I'd say not yet. We're not offering simpler, more accessible training in

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219 negotiation to all those who will need it in the future. I'm talking about
220 negotiation courses as the foundation. Then, of course, it can evolve—you
221 can study mediation and how mediators work. But the base is negotiation.
222 Today in my talk I used a key expression—and I'd be happy if you quote
223 this—the idea of a *common language*. If two professionals at the table don't
224 share that language—if I say "position" and I say "interest" and you don't
225 know what I mean—well, that's exactly where the gap lies between
226 academia
and practice.

227 S01: This is interesting, because it leads to the next point: how would you
228 bridge it? How do you think it can be bridged?

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229 S00: Surely, as I mentioned, through dedicated courses. Perhaps in Italy
230 the problem is that a specific academic discipline for this field doesn't
231 yet exist, right? It may sound a bit utopian, but... can I say that in the
232 interview?

233 S01: They're working on it.

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234 S00: Exactly—that for sure. And in my view, once that's in place, the
235 interaction will come naturally. You see it in all other fields, in law as
236 well as in economics: once you train professionals who go into the market,
237 those same professionals create a kind of feedback loop—they return to the
238 university, and there's an exchange. With negotiation, I don't see this
239 happening.

240 S01: So there's a missing virtuous cycle that should be triggered by
241 academia.

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242 S00: Yes, that's the easier lever. Sure, the market could ask for it, but
243 the problem is—I don't know if you agree—that even today negotiation is
244 still seen as a kind of "non-subject." Many in the legal world—ask lawyers
245 and they'll say—that to negotiate you just need experience. So there isn't
246 really a perceived need. And often what is meant by "negotiating" isn't the
247 fuller sense we intend, but simply finding a midpoint or a compromise.
248 That's why I think it's harder for change to come from practice. If
249 academia—the university—recognizes negotiation, then yes, it may be more
250 complicated organizationally, but it's also more effective. Up to now the
251 market hasn't really demanded it. I don't see a strong push from law firms,
252 for example—no one is asking universities to provide negotiation skills. If
253 I may—without boring you—let me add something. Students often tell me
that

254 when they apply for jobs, if they have studied economics and list a
255 negotiation course on their CV, companies notice it. How they interpret it,
256 I don't know—maybe they think, "he'll make us lots of profit"—but at least
257 they pause on it. In the legal world, though—and again I'm just reporting
258 what students tell me—it's usually ignored. No one asks about it; they
259 don't even notice it

260 S01: Yes—(.) in the legal domain, let's say, it's even more delicate. As a
261 trainer in the corporate world, I generally find there's more permeability
262 in business than in the legal sphere. As you say, sometimes lawyers feel
263 they already know how to do it, and so the first step to address a need is
264 missing. I like a metaphor: the half-empty glass—becoming aware of the
265 missing part lets us fill it. Now a question on a theme that seems very

266 dear to you: in your view, could members of civil society be included in
267 the process of closing this gap?

268 S00: I know this one—I know this one. You're giving me the chance to say
269 what I tried to outline today at the conference. One idea that comes to
270 mind—because it's what we've been working on—is to begin training from
271 an
272 early age. That's the idea I presented today (there are others, but let's
273 not get into them now). Specifically, I described a program for children in
274 third and fourth grade. What we did was take a university course in
275 negotiation and rework it—obviously with the help of people who specialize
276 in working with children—simplifying the concepts and seeing how kids
277 respond. The goal is first and foremost to create responsible citizens—to
278 form people. Because, as I said today, children are not only citizens of
279 the future; they are already fully human now—and they will surprise you.
280 They have to deal with emotions and tensions, but they lack the
281 language—the *common language*—to describe them. That's the experiment:
282 to
283 see whether giving them words—naming things—helps calm them. Seeing a
284 child
285 use the word "conflict," or say "negotiation," or talk about
286 "appreciation"—that's a lot. It's an experiment, but I believe civil
287 society could help close many gaps. I'll be brief so as not to bore you. We
288 often talk about cultural aspects—interculturality, differences in
289 negotiating across cultures—but let me pose it as a *what if*. We'll always
290 be different; we'll always have different identities. But *what if* we could
291 build a common cultural base—the culture of negotiation—if children
292 everywhere studied it from a young age? Maybe that would become a small
293 part of everyone's identity. We would all still be different, but there
294 would be one small piece that's shared. Would it help?

292 S01: So we return to the idea of a common language—which is quite
293 beautiful.

293 Francesco, if you'd like, maybe you can add something.

294 S02: Yes, yes, yes—on this I find it very interesting: conflict resolution,
295 and how to graft it into learning from a young age—then it clearly becomes
296 a practice. I wanted to ask a few other questions. About the conference, we
297 said it aims to bridge the gap between professionals on the one hand and
298 practitioners on the other, right? It's a European conference, even if
299 several speakers weren't European.

300 S00: Well, we're inclusive.

301 S02: // Sure, sure, sure. And we'd like to ask you about the distinctive
302 features of "European" negotiation. So—what are they? Are there particular
303 traits in Europe that characterize how negotiation is done here?

304 S00: Look, I couldn't say there are specific traits in the European way of
305 negotiating, because—as we always say—negotiation can be approached
306 scientifically, and then we like to say it becomes an art, since *you* are
307 the instrument. From what I've seen at this conference, we're very
308 advanced
309 in many aspects—though not uniformly. Some have gone further in one
310 area,
311 others in another. In my view, this conference is a chance to start pooling
312 that knowledge. There are excellent professionals working, for example, on

311 the substantive side—on data. I've seen people already working on
312 artificial intelligence—on the construction and engineering of deals. And
313 there are others who are absolutely expert on the relational and
314 psychological side. As a continent, there's great richness here—even in
315 terms of research. I was struck to see young scholars as well—doctoral
work
316 already exploring this field. So I'd say it's the variety—the wide range of
317 experiences—that makes this the right time to start pooling our efforts.
318 Over lunch I had a thought, a bit complex, but another *what if*: imagine
319 that in Europe we continue to support research moving forward vertically,
320 but at the same time we also manage to create a common foundation for
321 training—a set of essentials we all need. That could be very useful. I
322 don't know if I've really answered your question—perhaps you were looking
323 for something else. But if you ask me to identify a distinctive trait, I
324 wouldn't point to a single one. Negotiators are too diverse for that. If
325 anything, I'd say an instinctive common trait is study. Of all the people
326 I've met here, I don't think anyone would even imagine negotiation without
327 theoretical preparation. So when lawyers say, "I have experience," or "I
328 have flair," I think this conference proves otherwise. Of course, you are
329 the instrument at the table, but the message is clear: you must prepare and
330 study. That's the basic point. A scientific approach has to be
331 there—otherwise, we wouldn't be here.

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332 S02: Yes—what you said earlier is fundamentally preparation, right? Yes.
333 Because sometimes you do see skepticism in the job market.

334 S00: Yes—but let me add this: when you go down this path, as we're all
335 doing, you start to notice just how much inefficiency there is in people's
336 behavior—even in the workplace, even among those who are highly
educated. I

337 see it: people who studied economics, perfect and impeccable from a
338 technical standpoint, yet I still notice what I'd call negotiating
339 inefficiency—an inability to communicate, information that gets lost. I see
340 this often. And so I conclude that negotiation is an invaluable
341 competence—it's the foundation. You can't be a lawyer without this
342 foundation, because you are dealing directly with conflicts. And you can't
343 be a CEO without it either.

344 S02: Right—and that already anticipates the next question, because there
345 are key competencies: study and preparation are also somewhat
substantive
346 to be able to negotiate and communicate well.

347 S00: Yes—sorry, I'm not doing it on purpose—it's just that I don't remember
348 exactly, so I'm speaking off the cuff. But this is indisputable, and
349 perhaps it's the effort we're all trying to make, don't you think? The idea
350 is that we've acquired these competencies and we pass them on to
younger

351 people. The way I see it: at a negotiating table there are always at least
352 two people. **If only one is more or less prepared and understands the**
353 **concepts, then we're closer to an art, because the other isn't prepared.**
354 **But if both are prepared—because the school or university system has**
given

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355 **them that foundation—then we're closer to a science. At that point,**
356 **they're**
communicating with a common language, they take the right amount of

357 **time,**
358 **and the agreement builds gradually.** A small example: this happened to
359 me recently. A colleague—with all due respect—the very first thing she said
360 was, “we have to be quick,” “either we close today or it doesn’t make
361 sense.”
362 “ And there was no real deadline at all. That kind of approach, I would
363 call negotiating incompetence (again, with respect to that colleague). Why
364 not take the time to evaluate the information properly, instead of rushing
365 to ask for an immediate offer or proposal? In fact, more elements emerged
366 later on. That, to me, is a clear lack of negotiating competence.

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365 S01: The term “incompetence” is a technical term.

366 S00: Exactly—yes of course...

367 S01: It seems quite apt. It highlights a lack of competence.

368 S02: What other competencies do you see as central for tomorrow’s
369 negotiator?

370 S00: Well, if we’re talking about negotiation, it really encompasses
371 everything. So maybe I’ll put it this way: for me, negotiation can’t exist
372 without psychological concepts—because the relationship is always
373 involved,
374 our psychology and our mind—so, psychological and neuroscientific
375 aspects

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376 first. Then logic and mathematics, which I believe are the foundation. And
377 if we talk about “extra” competencies beyond those basics, I’d say they’re
378 not really extra. Even something as simple as tone of voice or effective
379 communication—in all its forms—becomes important. We could call it a
380 communicative path, even theatrical, whatever it may be. All of this, in my
381 view, helps strengthen the negotiation dimension. It’s always about human
382 interaction. This also makes me think—maybe we can look at it from the
383 opposite angle—about artificial intelligence. In my view the foundation
384 must always be human interaction, and I imagine one day there will be
385 so-called negotiation between machines. But let’s set that aside, because
386 when that happens there’s little we can do. The real point is this: perhaps
387 the key competence is learning to use AI—for example, in the preparation
388 and analysis phases. That’s already reality, and I would recommend it.
389 While you and I are at the table, being able to analyze data, have it
390 summarized, simulate outcomes or even generate ideas with AI certainly
391 helps if the goal is to reach an agreement. So one competence beyond the
392 basics could definitely be this: using AI as an enabling tool. But when AI
393 actually replaces the person sitting at the table, then we’re no longer
394 talking about negotiation—we’re talking about calculation. That’s why, in
395 my view, we should minimize as much as possible—even through legislative
396 measures that recognize the right to human interaction—the number of
397 interactions between machines and however avoiding them to be presented
398 as
399 real negotiations.

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397 S01: That opens philosophical debates.

398 S00: Yes—philosophical debates, and legal ones too. You have to ask
399 whether
400 there’s a mandate given to the machine, whether there isn’t, and if that

400 mandate is valid... a whole world opens up there. But honestly, I find it
401 less interesting than what we're discussing, because in that case it's
402 really just about whether the machines were well-programmed, whether
they
403 produce a result among themselves, and then simply accepting it. And at
404 that point, as I said before, it's no longer negotiation—it's just
405 calculation.

406 S01: Even the acceptance part isn't trivial. (..)

407 S00: Exactly. And then it becomes a legal issue—you must have the right,
408 for example, not to accept an interaction with a machine.

409 S01: You know that in some systems there's an automated decision-making
410 process, but there must always be the possibility of a human review—a
411 second level of interaction with a person. What do you think about that?

412 S00: Of course. But I think it's important to clarify that human review and
413 the right to human interaction are two very different things. Human review
414 concerns the decision—it's about checking or validating the outcome of an
415 automated process. The right to human interaction, instead, concerns the
416 person. It's about ensuring that every individual has the possibility of a
417 direct human relationship, not just a review of the decision made by a
418 machine. They are two distinct dimensions: one is procedural, the other is
419 existential. The first protects the correctness of the decision, while the
420 second protects human dignity //

421 S01: For now—who knows about the future—in Italy, in this case we're
422 referring to the GDPR; I don't know about the second-level decision part.
423 But the AI Act is brand new; we're still just approaching it legally from
424 this standpoint.

425 S02: Yes, we're moving toward the end—just a few last questions. Another
426 question we prepared concerns research in the field of negotiation. We
were
427 asking for impressions and ideas about possible research questions that
428 should be pursued at university level. In your view, what are the most
429 important—and still unanswered—research questions in negotiation?

430 S00: Look, one thing I'm really passionate about is the effect of
431 negotiation training—education—on the brain. I realize that stated like
432 this it sounds very general, so let me be more specific. My question is: if
433 we could compare—though it wouldn't be easy—two individuals, one who
434 follows traditional training, absorbing technical and logical concepts
435 (private law, for example), attending lectures and studying, and another
436 who undergoes negotiation training, which necessarily involves human
437 interaction—how would their brains respond differently? You might ask why
438 this matters, and what the effect would be. I'm curious because, from
439 simple observation—not scientifically proven—I notice that students who
440 take a negotiation course, or professionals who have followed this path,
441 seem to display higher abilities.

442 S02: So we're talking about human interaction.

443 S00: What effect does it have? That's the question. And I think this could
444 open up a broad field of research. After all, the brain is still a
445 mysterious, largely unknown area. I don't know how feasible it would be to

446 set up this kind of study right now, but that's the idea. For now, it's
447 only a hope: that by going through this path, perhaps aggressiveness
448 decreases—maybe we could discover that this kind of interaction, this
449 training rooted in study, produces positive effects. Apparently it
450 seems—how can I put it—that people who practice negotiation, people in
451 this
452 environment, tend to develop that capacity. Maybe we do it out of
453 necessity—because when you're there, you can't just fight—but in my view,
454 it does produce that effect. That's why I think this is the most important
455 area.

455 S02: Good—then we'll save the last question, because otherwise it doesn't
456 fit—it's a simpler one. I wanted to ask you, if you had to choose a book or
457 a film— //

458 S01: a book *that* is a film— (.) //

459 S02: what would you recommend? (.)

460 S00: Good question—I hadn't thought about it. Obviously, let's exclude my
461 own book. What would I recommend? Well, as for a book, I'd say *Beyond*
462 *Reason*. The reason is this: there are many other important books on
463 negotiation, but this one, in my view, goes a bit beyond the standard
464 frameworks. At least as I perceived it, it gives you the ability—through a
465 rational mechanism—to rationally understand the irrational. It helps you
466 see how and why other people's minds—and your own—can be influenced,
467 managed, and directed in different ways. That's why I'd recommend *Beyond*
468 *Reason* by Fisher and Shapiro. As for a film... good question. Here I'm a bit
469 unprepared... a film...

470 S01: Let's do this: we'll leave that open, so we'll have the chance to
471 speak again. And I'm very glad you chose *Beyond Reason*, because it's one
472 of
473 my favorite books ever.

473 S00: Exactly—I'll think about the film for a moment. As for the book, I
474 don't know how you found it, but I'd say it really opens your mind. Maybe
475 because my background is legal, it took me into an unexplored world—how
476 the
477 brain works. You learn a lot. So yes, I would recommend it. There's also
478 the Italian edition, translated as *Il negoziato emotivo*.

478 S00: It's not exactly a brilliant translation.

479 S00: Not super effective—but anyway. Okay, folks—so, I'll think about the
480 film. Unfortunately I failed on that one... I'll think about it now.

481 S01: Thanks so much for your availability—all-around—because beyond the
482 interview, your willingness is always evident. So, thanks a lot.

483 S00: Thank you—and compliments on the initiative. Absolutely. Full
484 availability for everything—for the whole group.

485 S01: Thank you very much!